

Polymorphisms: How They Drive Human Evolution

The most common example of mutations is in the visual appearance of humans: freckles, hair color, and skin color. The MC1R gene that codes for melanin was mutated, randomly, to present a certain component of the gene in a different code, leaving behind a difference in skin and hair pigment. Differences are evident in different areas of the world where skin pigments face natural selection in the environment. Lighter skin colors have an easier chance of thriving in colder climates where UV radiation is less prominent, while darker skin tones are present in regions closer to the equator (ScienceDaily, 2017). Mutations are the driving factor behind every human genomic development, including their contribution and presence to disease. Many genomic diseases stem from a particular class of genes in the immune system. The Major Histocompatibility Complex (MHC) system is polygenic and polymorphic, best known for its ability to bind peptide fragments--derived from pathogens that synthesize abnormal proteins--to the cell surface for T-Cells to destroy (Janeway, 2001). Janeway explains that the MHC is the most complex and unknown part of the immune system, consisting of several genes that are vulnerable to transposable elements (TEs), also known as jumping genes, that enter the genome during cell replication and protein synthesis and alter the expression of the gene. While these TEs may be responsible for instigating diseases like cancer and hemophilia, research argues that these elements are critical to ensuring embryonic survival given their responsibility with building the immune system to resist the pathogens that are presently mutating in their environment (Zhang, 2018). Mutations celebrate neither negative nor positive connotations. They are uncontrollable changes in DNA that belong to a neutral party, deriving from genomes that are vulnerable to jumping genes. Polymorphisms, L1s, TEs, and jumping genes are used

interchangeably to describe the 'jumping' of elements around and onto genes prior to them being copied and expressed. Similar to viruses, the genes have no intent to harm the host cell. They just want to replicate themselves, specifically during embryonic development. With the help of polymorphisms, humans will be further educated on the potential of mutations as the drive for human evolution, starting with their impact on embryonic cells.

Jumping genes are significantly greater in number and influence than genes in the human genome. Jumping genes make up half of three billion DNA bases, while genes only make up 1 percent of that number. Yella Hewings-Martin, author of the article, "Jumping genes made us human, but can they cause disease?" explains jumping genes as, "mobile DNA that can move from one location in the genome to another" (Martin, 2017). Bacteria use jumping genes frequently, letting them adapt to environmental pressures like antibiotic resistance. But genes also jump when bacteria or viruses infect humans. The cells usually counteract them, but there are a small number of jumping genes that become established in the cells, enhancing genetic diversity (Martin, 2017). Today, jumping genes are the most popular in early embryonic development, with both positive and negative results. Mobile DNA can jump to another location each time a cell divides, meaning they'll be passed on to the next generation. Linker's examination of mobile DNA in "Examining non-LTR retrotransposons in the context of the evolving primate brain," writes that the chances of that range from "1 in 20 to 1 in 1,000 births," meaning disruptions in normal gene functions are possible and can result in heritable diseases (Linker, 2017). On a positive note, the HERVK jumping gene, a remnant of an infection by an ancient retrovirus from around 200,000 years ago, is switched on during early human embryonic development. This retrovirus is capable of granting an embryo viral resistance (Reus,

2001). Transposable elements have also driven mutations. The cortex gene-responsible for changing the color of the dark moth's scales, was a likely victim of the jumping gene. Wing scales develop color depending on the speed at which they grow. The less proteins there are, the slower the growth and the darker the color of the scale. The more proteins there are, the more light and colorful the scales. The result of the gene mutating in a way that it darkens the moth's scale color was driven by jumping genes and led moths to survive under natural selection. A more random mutation that occurred was human evolution beyond the use of tails. Bo Xia, a graduate student studying genome evolution at New York University's (NYU) Grossman School of Medicine, reflects on a childhood memory. He says he "wondered as a child why people didn't have tails, and a tailbone injury a few years ago renewed his curiosity." After looking into it, he found a change in the gene that codes for tails, TBXT: "a short DNA insertion called an Alu element." The Alu element is a popular jumping gene, known for causing many mutations in the MHC. Retrotransposons--jumping genes that interrupt DNA synthesis during RNA translation-- are known for instigating retroviruses using the Alu insertion. They comprise 21% of the human genome, and include nuclear elements (Wang, 2020). Jumping genes are spread around the molecular genome and are responsible for instigating many mutations present in humans currently.

Polymorphisms are critical for embryonic development, and their impact on the current human genome will drive evolution as the MHC is mutated by TEs to fight against mutating pathogens. The challenge is that humans cannot control polymorphisms, and events and processes that can't be controlled are understood negatively. Polymorphisms have impacted the MHC the most, particularly in the MHC's Class III. Class III is a group of proteins identified

between MHC Classes I and II that can't classify as one of the two classes exclusively. This cluster is associated with signaling more than it is in immune response. They're found on the short arm of human chromosome 6, and are usually produced by liver cells and white blood cells (Wikipedia, 2022). The cluster has several retroelements (internal genes that move by RNA through translation in protein synthesis) including the human endogenous retrovirus (HERV) and Alu elements that have connections to lung problems. The region is one of the most complex gene clusters in the human genome. The MHC Class II is most popularly studied in terms of how genetic variants have impacted the region. Vasiliki Matzaraki writes that the MHC is incredibly susceptible to disease, implying that "impaired antigen presentation or unstable MHC class II molecules contribute to insufficient CD4+ T-cell responses," increasing susceptibility to infections (Matzaraki, 2017). These genes impact signaling proteins that control the host cell's response. For example, in the HLA, the human part of the MHC, Zhu Meng details several diseases derived from the HLA, including celiac disease, Graves' disease, type 1 diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, psoriasis vulgaris and idiopathic achalasia (Meng, 2016). Transposons are jumping around the MHC and instigating changes that propel evolution, starting with the production of genetic differences that drive natural selection.

To argue that mutations are inherently bad undermines the potential of a mutation to drive evolution in a population. Polymorphisms can affect stem cell differentiation, particularly with neurons. Haig Kazazian published from his study on jumping genes impacting stem cells, "Rat adult hippocampus neural stem cells during protein synthesis differentiated into neurons rather than glial cells, implying that L1s can affect cell fate" (Kazazian, 2005). He continues, "We thought retrotransposition events normally only occurred in germ cells, or in very early

development, the first cell stages. This is the first evidence these events might be occurring in developing neurons seen in the adult brain.” Albeit fearful for diseases that might appear from mutations occurring in the brain, the possibility of those mutations affecting stem cells and cell differentiation opens new pathways to mass producing neurons and other cells that are hard to come by without cloning or nuclear transfer. The presence of polymorphisms in embryonic stem cells is also evolutionary. Zhao Zhang, a member of the Carnegie research group who developed techniques for tracking jumping genes, conducted a study on the presence of jumping genes in embryonic stem cells. He found that these viral jumping genes are using nurse cells in an egg cell to manufacture and mass produce themselves, making them large in numbers. Patrizia Vitullo, who experimented with retrotransposons in mouse embryos, found that these jumping genes were not only present, but utilized. Looking at LINE-1 retro jumping genes--which belong to the Alu family--and nothing their presence in embryonic development, Vitullo concluded, “RT-dependent amplification of LINE-1 retrotransposons is a distinctive feature of early embryonic genomes,” and were involved in the development of mouse embryos preimplantation (Vitullo, 2012). Jumping genes are used in embryonic stem cells for development and have affected the fate of many undifferentiated cells, including cells that have differentiated to neurons. As diseases like dementia eat at neurons in the brain, humans aren’t able to reproduce those neurons at the same pace. An increased production of neurons through controlled stem cell differentiation can ensure neurons are reproducing enough to mitigate the effects of such diseases. Jumping genes are also able to stimulate immune antiviral response in tumor-specific cells after activation occurs over a loss in DNA methylation (Kong, 2019). The loss of DNA methylation (from environmental causes like drug exposure), responsible for repressing

transcription in protein synthesis, foreshadows many cancers, but it also activates jumping genes that trigger an immune antiviral response (Moore, 2012). The reactivation of tumor-specific jumping genes could synergize with immunotherapy as it creates neoantigens designed to help the body respond to forming cancer cells, leading to the end of cancer. Perhaps the greatest benefit of jumping genes is their comparable effectiveness to CRISPR software and other gene-editing tools in revolutionizing gene therapy. Given that jumping genes already jump around the genome and have the instructions to do so, it is easier for scientists to take advantage of jumping genes than use CRISPR, which is more unnatural than a man-made jumping gene, to perform gene therapy. When Sayani Basu looked into the man-made transposon “Sleeping Beauty (SB10)” that launched in 1997, she found that “It [SB10] is safer than virus-based gene therapy. Gene editing through the CRISPR-CAS9 is a tedious job but the SB system-based gene editing is simpler yet effective” (Basu, 2020). While jumping genes are responsible for mutations that have led to several diseases, they are just as credited with instigating responses in signaling proteins to attack viral and cancerous cells threatening to enter the human genome, and those changes can be controlled or uncontrolled.

In an interview conducted with Trino Asencio-Ibanez, a professor in the Molecular Biochemistry Department at NC State University, he summarized his research with viruses in the molecular genome. He argued that the relationship between a virus and a genome is “adaptive”, meaning the virus is always adapting to the genome’s immune system and the genome is always trying to respond to the virus’ changes. “The virus has no malicious intent towards the host,” He explains, “but there are circumstances where the virus overpowers the host and kills it.” This is one of many possible results, and an expectation of natural selection. Jumping genes share the

same relationship with the molecular genome. They jump around in stem cells during the cell cycle and bring both problems and solutions to the cell by instigating mutations. They are numerous and reckless and are more likely to instigate disease more than they are thriving genetic differences. But they are also used during embryonic development to protect the body from infection. With each environmental change that happens and drives viruses to invade the human genome, the MHC has to be ready to trigger an antiviral response. Jumping genes have demonstrated a quality in them that, although uncontrolled, can regulate the MHC when it experiences DNA hypomethylation. They also hold great potential as a natural but controllable way to successfully facilitate gene therapy, and they're greatly influential in the cloning field with their ability to facilitate stem cell differentiation. Jumping genes are constantly evolving around the genome to survive, and the genome is always changing around jumping genes. If the death of one person from a mutation is evaluated without considering the survivability of a group as a whole, the benefits or consequences of a mutation are only being viewed at an individual level, concerning one person, and not on a population level, which is where the potential for evolution lies. Taking advantage of the environment and the vast potential of jumping genes in the human genome will demonstrate the ability of humans to mitigate the effects of natural selection in a population, making them inherently beneficial for genetic variation and evolution.

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